

DIRECTIONS D5.2:

Report on the stability analysis of an offshore electrical energy hub, considering grid-forming control strategies

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Executive Summary

This report constitutes the second deliverable in the DIRECTIONS project for Work Package 5 (WP5), which applies to *Task 5.2* and *Task 5.3*. The overall approach for the deliverables of Work Packages 2 and 5 is illustrated in Fig. 1. This deliverable focuses on the application of the tools developed in Work Package 2 to relevant case studies.

The report presents a comprehensive small-signal stability analysis of an offshore Electrical Energy Hub (EEH) integrating large-scale offshore wind generation, Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC)-based High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) transmission, and parallel AC/DC cable-based interconnections. The studies adopt the frequency-domain framework to systematically assess the system dynamics under a wide range of operating conditions, control strategies, and parameters.

A detailed model of the EEH is developed in the electromagnetic transient (EMT) software PSCAD. The model includes the frequency-dependent representation of the AC and DC cables, aggregated offshore wind farms operating in Grid-Following (GFL) mode, as well as HVDC converters operating in both Grid-Forming (GFM) and GFL modes. The frequency-domain characterization and analysis are performed using the openly available *Z-tool*, which allows for flexible analysis including black-box models, i.e. it does not require the explicit dynamic equations governing the different subsystems. In particular, the small-signal dynamics are evaluated based on state-of-the-art methods such as the Generalized Nyquist Criterion (GNC), Resonance Mode Analysis (RMA), and the Phase Shift Criterion (PSC). This multi-metric approach ensures a reliable identification of oscillatory modes, dominant interactions among subsystems, and instability mechanisms.

The EEH system is analyzed under multiple configurations, including variations in power flow, offshore topologies, control architectures and parameters, and external grid conditions. The results demonstrate that frequency-domain methods provide reliable predictions of the small-signal dynamics, as consistently validated through EMT simulations. This confirms their suitability for efficiently screening different operating scenarios to identify any critical dynamic interactions and associated subsystems.

Based on the findings, the report provides key recommendations for both

system analysis and design. From a small-signal perspective, it highlights the importance of evaluating multiple operating conditions and network configurations, ensuring sufficient frequency resolution, adopting realistic component models, and combining complementary stability metrics. From a design and operational viewpoint, coordinated control strategies, appropriate DC voltage controller tuning, and sufficiently fast AC voltage regulation are identified as critical factors to ensure stable operation.

Overall, this work establishes a systematic framework and delivers practical insights to support the development of stable, scalable, and resilient EEHs, facilitating higher integration of renewable energy through HVDC-based interconnections.

Figure 1: DIRECTIONS control approach: this report’s contents are in green.

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